

The RESIST/ANCE Game PnP

Introduction

Welcome to RESIST/ANCE, an empowering, mission-driven, strategic, **collaborative game**, where you can develop strategies to fight oppression, inequalities and injustice. We are delighted that you have a copy of this game, and hope that you find it engaging.

This is a game of interactive play, aimed at developing capacity together to counter 'anti-gender' mobilisations, or **Challenges**. This game helps us do this by exploring how such mobilisations operate, the real-world impacts they have, and **Strategies** to resist them in a space where you can reflect, learn, and act together. The goal is to create collective long-term **Resilience** to build better worlds.

Printing Instructions

You can request a printed pack of this game via the project coordinator Kath Browne (kath.browne@ucd.ie), or you can print this PnP (Print and Play) .pdf version of the game.

For the full set of RESIST/ANCE resources, including the RESIST/ANCE PnP Game, scan this QR code... <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

What Is In This Resource?

In this accompanying resource of the RESIST/ANCE game, you will find information regarding:

- What you will need for printing
- Printing, step by step
- How to prepare the card components for play
- A list of the other components you will need to gather to play
- RESIST/ANCE Card Game printable
- Publication information

There are 101 playing **Cards**, all of which show prompts derived from the data gathered by the RESIST Project:

- 15 Challenge Cards
- 40 Event Cards
- 46 Strategy Cards
- of which 10 are Synergy Cards

In addition, there are:

- 19 Wild Cards which you can customise as Strategy or Challenge Cards
- 15 (5 sets of three) double-sided Information Cards, **a set of each of which can be dealt to each player at Setup**: (1) a Quick Setup Card, (2) a Quick Rules Card and (3) a handy QR Codes Card

What You Will Need For Printing

- Access to a printer, and
- 16 sheets of white paper (15 sheets of cards and one test sheet if you wish), ideally smooth 300gsm cardstock for easier shuffling, but anything 100gsm and over will work fine.

This PnP (Print and Play) version of the RESIST/ANCE game is available from the RESIST Zenodo repository, linked above, and is included below in this document.

Printing, Step By Step

You can print in full colour, or black and white, as you wish; the game will work either way. **Aim to print the pages as large as they will print on a standard A4 size sheet (210 x 297 mm), without losing any of the edges of the images.** There will be nine cards per printed sheet. Check out your printing options, and choose options like 'Scale to fit', 'Scale to 100%' or 'Print entire image'. It is **important that all pages are printed using the same options** for the entire set of fifteen pages so that the front and backs of the cards line up on both sides of the printed sheets.

Pages in the .pdf are in the order Sheet 1 front, Sheet 1 back, Sheet 2 front, Sheet 2 back, etc. These instructions will show you how to print one sheet of cards, front and back, at a time. You may wish to do a test print for the first sheet.

Feed your first blank sheet into your printer, ensuring the sheet is centered in the printer loading tray. This will print page 1, i.e. the front of the first page of cards. Once that page is printed, load the same sheet into the printer again the same orientation/way up as it was loaded when printing side 1, but with the blank side ready to print. Print page 2 of the document. This will print the back of the first sheet of cards on the blank side of your first sheet. You now have the first sheet of cards printed both front and back.

Repeat this process for the remaining fourteen pages of cards, printing the front and then the back of each sheet, one page at a time.

Preparation of Card Components

You should have fifteen pages of cards, ready to cut out. We recommend that you cut with the front of the cards facing you or ease of accuracy. If you have a guillotine, that would be a relatively quick way to cut the cards out; however, scissors will work well too. Consider sitting together to cut the cards out collaboratively, and discuss the themes as you discover them, before playing. Don't worry if they don't cut quite right, as it is the experience of the game that matters.

You Will Also Need

A **Resilience Tracker Sheet** printable, which you can download from the RESIST Zenodo Repository. This will help you to keep track of progress in the game, via **Resilience Points (RPs)**, but also your own reflections. Print one Resilience Tracker Sheet for the team, or have one per player for **personal takeaways, reflection notes and follow up Actions**—it's up to you! Download via the QR code above...
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504652>

Rules of play. You may have a physical copy, but if not, you can read these online, or print them out. These resources are available via the QR code above.

Die A physical die, a die app on your phone, or Google dice roller. A die is used for some decision making in the game. If you don't have a die, have someone pick a random number between 1 and 6 when required.

Pen You can use a pen to customise the cards and to fill in your Resilience Tracker.

Enjoy!
The RESIST Team

PRINT using the printing instructions, in this document, or on the RESIST website, on 13 sheets of A4 paper, front and back. You can print either in colour or black & white —the game will work either way.

CUT out all nine playing cards on each of the sheets you have printed using the vertical and horizontal cut lines as your guides. You can be extra, and round the cards if you wish by cutting off the rounded corners.

PLAY using the game rules outlined in the Rules Booklet. CUSTOMISE the game to reflect your context, and COLLABORATE using your Strategies to tackle Challenges and unexpected Events.

3 Strategy &

Speaking Up in Daily Life

You speak up against 'anti-gender' narratives in the workplace

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy &

Speaking Up in Daily Life

You speak up against 'anti-gender' narratives in family settings

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy &

Speaking Up in Daily Life

You express your views to your friends and acquaintances

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy &

Personal Conversations

By sharing your experiences, in settings where you feel safe, you foster empathy

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy &

Personal Conversations

You participate in events and projects that foster dialogue and understanding within civil society

Customise this card for your context...

2 Strategy &

Setting Clear Boundaries

You set clear boundaries by speaking out

Customise this card for your context...

2 Strategy &

Setting Clear Boundaries

You set clear boundaries by refusing to engage with harmful narratives

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Withdrawal

You choose to withdraw yourself from visibility as an act of survival

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Withdrawal

You choose anonymity as an act of survival

Customise this card for your context...

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1 Strategy

Secrecy

You choose secrecy to protect yourself

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Bridging Divides

You are committed to and facilitate intergenerational dialogue, to bridge divides, promote diverse perspectives and address conflicts

Customise this card for your context...

1 Strategy

Shaping the Narrative

You shape the narrative by telling your own stories on your own terms

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy &

Celebrating in Public

You organise creative public campaigns and Pride events to promote your visibility

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy &

Celebrating in Public

You organise creative public campaigns and Pride events to empower participants and other affected individuals

Customise this card for your context...

5 Strategy &

Joyful Gatherings

You organise joyful gatherings where you celebrate your resilience, make new friends and recharge your batteries together; joy is the fuel for a long fight for justice

Customise this card for your context...

1 Strategy

Community Classes

You and your organisation run community-led classes on digital safety, advocacy skills and self-defence in order to directly empower individuals

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Community Spaces

You participate in creating safe and welcoming community spaces for those affected by 'anti-gender' politics, where they can network, share their experiences and organise themselves

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Claiming Public Space

You listen to and acknowledge those in your community who are multiply-marginalised

Customise this card for your context...

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4 Strategy

Claiming Public Space

You have sufficient resources and can therefore stay vocal

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Claiming Public Space

You support multiply-marginalised members of your community in being heard and seen

Customise this card for your context...

2 Strategy

Psychosocial Peer Support

You organise a peer support group for your community

Customise this card for your context...

2 Strategy

Psychosocial Peer Support

You find support in the services offered by your trusted community organisation, network or collective

Customise this card for your context...

2 Strategy

Collaborating With Journalists

Your community organisation, network or collective builds relationships with journalists committed to accurate and respectful reporting

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Professional Support Networks

You join community organisations, networks or collectives to find space for mutual support

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Professional Support Networks

You share resources amongst your community organisations, networks or collectives

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Professional Support Networks

Your community organisation, network or collective liaises with others to create coordinated responses to attacks

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Respond Collectively

Your community shows solidarity to those who are multiply-marginalised and collaborates with other relevant community groups

Customise this card for your context...

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3 Strategy

Legal Counselling

Your community organisation, network or collective provides access to legal advice

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Legal Counselling

You take up free legal advice provided by your trusted community organisation, network or collective

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Legal Counselling

You provide access to legal advice and help others facing legal challenges

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Safety Audits and Protocols

You work with your community to develop comprehensive security measures for venues, events and online platforms

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Safety Audits and Protocols

To ensure everyone's safety at venues, events and online platforms, you collaborate with law enforcement agencies

Customise this card for your context...

5 Strategy

Capacity Building

You and your community build capacity for digital campaigns and the strategic use of social media in order to reach the general public with your concerns

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Address Intersectionality

You and your organisation ensure that community structures meet the needs of multiply-marginalised people

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Address Intersectionality

You and your organisation create dedicated spaces and platforms where multiply-marginalised people can make their voices heard

Customise this card for your context...

5 Strategy

Protest

You organise collective protests and counter-protests

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1 Strategy

Engage Institutions

You work with your funders and/or employer to mitigate hostility and offences

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Transnational Alliances

Your community organisation, network or collective joins a transnational alliance of organisations that strengthen each other by pooling resources

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Transnational Alliances

Your community organisation, network or collective supports other community groups by sharing your knowledge

Customise this card for your context...

4 Strategy

Transnational Alliances

Your community organisation, network or collective joins a transnational alliance of organisations to strengthen advocacy across borders

Customise this card for your context...

2 Strategy

Engaging Government

Your community actively engages with policy makers to raise their awareness

Customise this card for your context...

2 Strategy

Engaging Government

Your community actively engages with policy makers to secure important financial resources for services and initiatives

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Fostering Allyship

Your community builds relationships with politicians in order to generate greater public understanding and support

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Fostering Allyship

Your community builds relationships with journalists to generate greater public understanding and support

Customise this card for your context...

3 Strategy

Fostering Allyship

Your community builds relationships with artists to generate greater public understanding and support

Customise this card for your context...

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3 Strategy

Fostering Allyship

Your community builds relationships with companies to generate greater public understanding and support

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Vilification in Staged “Debates”

The media, religious and political actors stage a debate about your community in which they reinforce one-sided narratives and spread misinformation

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Public Misrepresentation

As LGBTIQ+ individuals and feminist activists, you are stigmatised in reactionary political and media agendas and prevented from expressing yourselves in your own words

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Mocking and Misgendering in Public

Trans and non-binary people are ridiculed by ‘anti-gender’ actors in public debates about inclusive language, pronouns, and misgendering in public discourse, and are not recognised as subjects with rights

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Offences on Rights

‘Anti-gender’ actors challenge reproductive rights and obstruct reforms designed to facilitate abortion, reproductive health services, gender recognition and parenthood for same-sex couples

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Suppression of Gender Diversity and Equality Efforts

State suppression of queer and feminist activism by banning Pride events, prohibiting display of feminist banners in public, and banning queer, gender-neutral language; activists are monitored and arrested

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Instrumental Use of Parliamentary Procedures

Politicians submit parliamentary questions to scrutinise and delegitimise the funding of feminist and LGBTIQ+ projects

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Legal Intimidation

‘Anti-gender’ actors use strategic lawsuits to intimidate and silence feminist and queer activists, organisations, academics and authors—especially those who speak out publicly

Customise this card for your context...

7 Challenge

Workplace Punishment

As educators, activists and academics who campaign for feminist and queer rights, you face professional consequences and disciplinary measures

Customise this card for your context...

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Organisational Targeting

As a feminist and LGBTIQ+ organisation, you are confronted with politically motivated inspections, orchestrated threats, physical attacks on your office, protests outside your premises and strategic lawsuits

Customise this card for your context...

Intimidation of Academics

As academics, you experience attempts to influence your work, as well as delegitimisation and intimidation from within and outside the scientific community

Customise this card for your context...

Offences on Education

As educators who advocate for equality in the classroom, your work is targeted by 'anti-gender' actors through teaching bans, threats, lawsuits and smear campaigns

Customise this card for your context...

Digital Violence

You are affected by various forms of digital violence, such as cyberattacks on your website, doxing—publishing private information to intimidate someone—and cyberbullying

Customise this card for your context...

Harassment and Surveillance

As a feminist or queer public figure, you are exposed to verbal offences, threats, intimidation in public, surveillance, stalking, and targeted sexualised hate speech

Customise this card for your context...

Threats Against Pride

During a public Pride parade, you are disrupted by an extreme-right group that wants to spread fear and prevent you from campaigning for the rights of the LGBTIQ+ community

Customise this card for your context...

Physical Violence

As queer feminist activists and queer individuals, you are repeatedly confronted with physical violence and, in some cases, abuse by law enforcement agencies

Customise this card for your context...

Burnout

Continuous defamation causes deep exhaustion, disillusionment and ultimately burnout; you withdraw from activism or community work

Effect: Your resistance feels lowered; subtract one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Chilling Effect

'Anti-gender' attacks and possible legal consequences cause you to feel afraid, prompting you to withdraw both from public debate and your visible role in society

Effect: One of your usual Strategies is not within reach; discard one card at random from your Defence Tableau. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along your Defence Tableau. Discard the card you land on.

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Event

Fleeting Solidarity

You are marginalised in multiple ways and feel uncomfortable even in feminist and LGBTIQ+ spaces; you feel alone and withdraw from the community

Effect: Fewer options for resistance are available; discard one card from the Strategy Toolkit. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along the top row of the Strategy Toolkit, continuing onto the next row if you reach the end of the current row. Roll the die again, and count down by the value rolled, wrapping around to the top of the next column of the Strategy Toolkit if necessary.

Event

Impact of Forced Migration

You fled your home country due to 'anti-gender' hostility; this triggers feelings of uprootedness and isolation and makes you fear for your social status and career

Effect: Your resistance feels lowered; subtract two Resilience Points by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Event

Abandonment

You have been the victim of an 'anti-gender' offence in the context of your work and feel let down, not only by the law enforcement authorities, but also by your employer; as a result, you have to resort to personal resources such as time and money to deal with the consequences

Effect: 'anti-gender' mobilisations increase in intensity; discard one card from your Defence Tableau. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along your Defence Tableau. Discard the card you land on. Do not refill your Defence Tableau until Stage 4: Rebalance.

Event

Spaces Become Harder to Access

Community services are becoming more hidden and less accessible to you in order to protect against offences or backlash

Effect: Fewer options for resistance are available; discard one card from the Strategy Toolkit. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along the top row of the Strategy Toolkit, continuing onto the next row if you reach the end of the current row. Roll the die again, and count down by the value rolled, wrapping around to the top of the next column of the Strategy Toolkit if necessary.

Event

Resources are Stretched Thin

As an organisation, you are forced to invest more and more of your valuable time and energy in dealing with the effects of offences; you have to deal with threats, trust building, security issues and community support

Effect: Your resistance feels lowered; subtract one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Event

Funding Dries Up as Demand Grows

Although demand for services is growing, as an organisation you are losing more and more financial resources—either because political support is being withdrawn or because donors fear being drawn into controversies

Effect: One of your usual Strategies is not within reach; discard one card at random from your Defence Tableau. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along your Defence Tableau. Discard the card you land on.

Event

Exclusion Within Communities

Harmful narratives about trans and non-binary people, sex workers, refugees, or people of colour take root within feminist and queer spaces—pushing those most affected to the margins

Effect: Fewer options for resistance are available; discard one card from the Strategy Toolkit. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along the top row of the Strategy Toolkit, continuing onto the next row if you reach the end of the current row. Roll the die again, and count down by the value rolled, wrapping around to the top of the next column of the Strategy Toolkit if necessary.

Event

Internal Conflict Weakens Solidarity

Tensions across generations, political stances and identities lead to open hostility, eroding solidarity and leading to growing disillusionment and even disengagement from the community altogether

Effect: Your resistance feels lowered; subtract two Resilience Points by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Event

Violence Becomes Normalised

Due to increasing threats, harassment and legal intimidations, you are withdrawing from participation in public life, which erodes open, democratic debate

Effect: 'anti-gender' mobilisations increase in intensity; discard one card from your Defence Tableau. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along your Defence Tableau. Discard the card you land on. Do not refill your Defence Tableau until Stage 4: Rebalance.

Event

Harmful Narratives Go Mainstream

Because reactionary ideas are increasingly accepted as 'common sense', it becomes easier for 'anti-gender' actors to justify oppression and harder for you to contest discrimination

Effect: Fewer options for resistance are available; discard one card from the Strategy Toolkit. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along the top row of the Strategy Toolkit, continuing onto the next row if you reach the end of the current row. Roll the die again, and count down by the value rolled, wrapping around to the top of the next column of the Strategy Toolkit if necessary.

Event

Rights Work Is Discredited

Because 'anti-gender' actors frame feminism and LGBTQ+ advocacy as threats to children, religion and society, civil society space is shrinking and democracy is being weakened

Effect: Your resistance feels lowered; subtract one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Event

Media and Political Debates Distort Reality

Staged controversies dominate public debate, with trans and queer people often being spoken about but not heard; stereotypes and misinformation thus replace facts and lived experiences

Effect: 'anti-gender' mobilisations increase in intensity; discard one card from your Defence Tableau. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along your Defence Tableau. Discard the card you land on. Do not refill your Defence Tableau until Stage 4: Rebalance.

Event

Academic Freedom is Under Threat

Scholars face pressure from political actors, risk losing funding, and face increased personal risk when researching topics such as gender or sexuality, sometimes avoiding public appearances or censoring themselves out of fear

Effect: Fewer options for resistance are available; discard one card from the Strategy Toolkit. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along the top row of the Strategy Toolkit, continuing onto the next row if you reach the end of the current row. Roll the die again, and count down by the value rolled, wrapping around to the top of the next column of the Strategy Toolkit if necessary.

Event

Marginalised Voices are Excluded

As a refugee, person of colour or person with disabilities, you face barriers and discrimination even within feminist and LGBTQ+ space; this limits inclusive, democratic decision making

Effect: Fewer options for resistance are available; discard one card from the Strategy Toolkit. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along the top row of the Strategy Toolkit, continuing onto the next row if you reach the end of the current row. Roll the die again, and count down by the value rolled, wrapping around to the top of the next column of the Strategy Toolkit if necessary.

Event

Civic Education is Undermined

By actively blocking educational efforts to promote understanding of gender and sexuality, 'anti-gender' actors are jeopardising long-term democratic engagement and education

Effect: 'anti-gender' mobilisations increase in intensity; discard one card from your Defence Tableau. Choose the card to discard using the die as follows: roll the die and, using the value rolled, count from left to right along your Defence Tableau. Discard the card you land on. Do not refill your Defence Tableau until Stage 4: Rebalance.

Event

Speaking Up to Push Back Against 'Anti-Gender' Narratives

You find ways to express yourself at work, with your family and your friends, and are able to push back against 'anti-gender' narratives

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Event

Sharing Lived Experiences and Creating Space

By sharing lived experiences and creating space for open dialogue you foster empathy and prevent extremist views from taking root

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Event

Setting Clear Boundaries

By speaking out vocally and by refusing to engage with harmful narratives you set clear boundaries against 'anti-gender' politics

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; deal two new cards to the Strategy Toolkit from the Strategy Deck, even if the Strategy Toolkit is already full

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Having Sufficient Resources and Claiming Public Space

You find ways to take up space, to stay vocal and to continue your important work publicly and thereby countering 'anti-gender' actors

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Receiving Psychosocial Peer Support

You find psychosocial support from others affected, which makes you feel seen, understood and safe

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Receiving Legal Counselling

You find accessible legal advice and receive support with your legal challenges

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; deal two new cards from the Strategy card deck to the Strategy Toolkit, even if the Strategy Toolkit is already full

Using Safety Measures

Your organisation develops a comprehensive security concept, allowing you to participate in events and to continue to network and strengthen your relationships without fear of offences by 'anti-gender' actors

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn two Resilience Points by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Hosting Community Classes to Convey Skills and Empower Individuals

You get the chance to participate in a community-led course on digital security and strengthen your advocacy and self-defence skills

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Capacity Building to Reach The General Public

Your organisation receives financial resources, enabling it to build capacity for digital campaigns and the strategic use of social media; this allows you to raise public awareness of your issues

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; deal two new cards from the Strategy card deck to the Strategy Toolkit, even if the Strategy Toolkit is already full

Creating Safe Community Spaces

Having access to a safe and welcoming community space makes you feel comfortable enough to share your experiences with others affected by 'anti-gender' politics and to get organised

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Addressing Intersectionality

The structures of your community meet your needs as a multiply-marginalised person and enable your voice to be heard, empowering you and giving you hope

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Bridging Divides

By being committed to and supportive of open and intergenerational dialogue, you and your organisation promote diverse perspectives and address conflicts which helps to bridge divides within the community

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; deal two new cards from the Strategy card deck to the Strategy Toolkit, even if the Strategy Toolkit is already full

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Collaborating With Journalists

By working with journalists who are committed to accurate and respectful reporting on the community, you and your organisation manage to challenge harmful stereotypes and share the history of, and expertise from, the community

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn two Resilience Points by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Creating Professional Support Networks

Because your organisation has networked with other LGBTIQ+ organisations, you now have the opportunity to benefit from their resources and support each other in the fight against 'anti-gender' actors

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Engage Institutions

Your employer supports you in defending yourself against hostility and offences in your work context by 'anti-gender' actors, which takes some of the pressure off you and conserves your resources

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Forming Transnational Alliances

By participating in forming a transnational alliance of organisations, you pool resources, share and acquire knowledge and strengthen advocacy efforts across borders

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Engage Government

You and your organisation find ways to raise awareness of your concerns among policy-makers, which brings you important financial resources for your vital and essential services and initiatives

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Foster Allyship

Your organisation has been able to build important relationships with politicians and thus gain greater public support for its causes

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; deal two new cards from the Strategy card deck to the Strategy Toolkit, even if the Strategy Toolkit is already full

Respond Collectively

By joining forces across community boundaries you are able to respond swiftly and powerfully to 'anti-gender' offences

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn two Resilience Points by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Shape the Narrative

By telling your own stories, on your own terms, you are able to shape the narrative

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Protest

By organising collective protests and counter-protests you resist 'anti-gender' politics

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; deal two new cards from the Strategy card deck to the Strategy Toolkit, even if the Strategy Toolkit is already full

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Celebrate in Public

By organising creative public campaigns and Pride events you promote your visibility and empower participants and other affected individuals

Effect: Your resistance grows; earn one Resilience Point by making a note on your Resilience Tracker sheet

Joyful Gatherings

You take part in joyful gatherings to celebrate your resilience, make new friends and recharge your batteries together, which fills you with joy and empowers you for a long fight for justice

Effect: You have developed a new resistance Strategy; draw one card from the Strategy Toolkit and place in your Defence Tableau, even if your Tableau then exceeds the stated maximum of five cards

Title:

Customise this card for your context...

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Customise this card for your context...

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Strategy / Challenge

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RESIST/ANCE
Game Rules

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RESIST/ANCE
Quick Setup

1. Shuffle the Strategy Cards and Deal a Strategy Toolkit 5x3
2. Deal a Defence Tableau 5x1
3. Place remaining Strategy Cards to the left of the Toolkit = Strategy Deck

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Rules: quick reference

Setup (see Quick Setup card) then play rounds of four stages:

Stage 1, What now!? Flip the top Event Card ⚡ and resolve its Effect ⚡

Stage 2, Strategise. Discuss which Strategies in your Defence Tableau could tackle the visible Challenges ? → 🟢

Stage 3, Act. For each visible Challenge:

- Play up to 1 Strategy Card from your Defence Tableau ✓ → 🟢

Stage 3, Synergise. If you play:

- A Synergy& Card onto another Strategy Card → +1 bonus Strength 🟡
- A Synergy& Card onto another Synergy& Card → +2 bonus Strength and +1 Resilience 🟡🟡🌀

Add total of played Strategy Strengths and Synergy& bonuses together = total Strength, per Challenge Σ / 🟢

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RESIST/ANCE Quick Setup

4. Shuffle the Challenge Cards and Deal a Challenge Horizon 4x1

5. Place remaining Challenge Cards to the left of the Challenge Horizon = Challenge Deck

6. Shuffle the Event Cards and place to the right of the Strategy Toolkit = Event Deck

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Rules: quick reference ctd.

- If total Strength played per Challenge Card \geq Challenge Strength \rightarrow Challenge is overcome \geq

Stage 3, Reflect. Bonus per named Action

Stage 4, Rebalance

- Gain Resilience equal to Strength of any completed Challenge \rightarrow
- Flip one hidden Challenge face up
- Refill Defence Tableau back to 5 cards from the Strategy Toolkit
- Optionally spend 2 Resilience to refill the Toolkit from the Strategy Deck

The **game ends**, when:

- All Challenges are overcome OR
- You cannot refill your Defence Tableau

Finally, count your Resilience and reflect together on what just happened

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AUTHOR Aoife Grant

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RESIST/ANCE—Strategies for a Better World

Based on the RESIST Research Project: www.theresistproject.eu

An output of the RESIST Research Project, ID:101060749

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